

ISOQUINOLINE DERIVATIVES. PART III

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In contrast with the earlier observation (Ghosh and Dutta, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 17, 755) that treatment of (α -acetamido- β -phenyl)-ethylmethyl ketone and of β -phenyl-substituted analogues with POCl_3 or conc. H_2SO_4 leads to the formation of 1-methylisoquinoline derivatives, accompanied with dehydrogenation and deacetylation, (α -acetamido- β -phenyl)-ethylphenyl ketone and β -phenyl-substituted analogues yield, under similar condition, oxazole derivatives. Methyl α -acetamido- α -methyl- β -phenylpropionate undergoes the Bischler-Napieralski cyclisation to yield the corresponding isoquinoline derivative. Condensation of α -acetamido- α -methyl- β -phenylpropionyl chloride with ethyl sodiomalonate leads to the formation of an oxazole derivative.

It has been shown (Ghosh and Dutta, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 17, 755) that treatment of (α -acetamido- β -phenyl)-ethylmethyl ketone with phosphorus oxychloride leads to the formation of 1-methylisoquinoline, the process involving cyclodehydration, dehydrogenation and deacetylation. The reaction can be effected by concentrated sulphuric acid as well and can be applied to β -phenyl-substituted analogues. However, it has been stated that the exact sequence of the three processes involved is not clear. In order to get an insight into the exact mechanism of the reaction, it is thought desirable to prepare analogous α -acylamidoketones with various substitutions and subject them to the action of such reagents as phosphorus oxychloride or concentrated sulphuric acid. Accordingly, α -acetamido- β -phenylpropionic acid and the corresponding *o*-chloro- and *p*-chloro-phenyl analogues have been subjected to the Dakin and West reaction (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1928, 78, 91, 745, 757) with benzoic anhydride in presence of pyridine to obtain the corresponding ketone (I). When treated with phosphorus oxychloride, (I) undergoes cyclisation with the formation of a non-basic compound, which is evidently represented by the oxazole structure (II) (cf. Wiley, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1947, 12, 43).

(I)

(II)

[R = Ph, *o*-Cl.C₆H₄, *p*-Cl.C₆H₄]

[III: X = H or Cl]

to provide the azlactone with an α -acetamido- β -keto acid and acetate ion, and the subsequent conversion of this azlactone into the acetamidoketone and carbon dioxide. This view is supported by Attenburrow *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 310), Cleland and Niemann (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 841) and Cornforth and Elliott (*Science*, 1950, 112, 534), and it is considered that only those α -amino-acids or their derivatives, which are capable of forming azlactones containing an active α -hydrogen atom, will undergo the Dakin and West reaction. Wiley (*Science*, 1950, 111, 259), however, rejects this mechanism in favour of an initial base-catalysed decarboxylation, the carbanion then reacting with the acetic anhydride or other carbonyl component to give rise to the corresponding ketone. The observation, now made, that the amino-acid (IV) does not respond to the Dakin and West reaction can, however, be explained on the basis of the azlactone mechanism, for no hydrogen atom replaceable by acetyl, is available in the azlactone (VII), which is capable of formation from (IV) *via* (VI). This observation, however, cannot be accommodated in Wiley's mechanism, as (VI) could provide a carbanion by decarboxylation.

It is noteworthy that the methyl ester of (VI), on cyclodehydration with POCl_3 , readily furnishes 1:3-dimethyl-3-carbomethoxy-3:4-dihydroisoquinoline (VIII: $\text{R}=\text{CO}_2\text{Me}$) as a reddish gummy mass, characterised as picrate. This was hydrolysed by 20% caustic soda solution to the acid (VIII: $\text{R}=\text{CO}_2\text{H}$).

An alternative route to (V), involving condensation of ethyl sodiomalonate with the acid chloride of (VI), results in the formation of a compound which is, however, devoid of ketonic property, does not exhibit any ferric reaction, and is slowly hydrolysed at room temperature by 5% aqueous caustic soda to the acid (VI). These properties and the analytical figures are in accord with the structure (X), evidently obtained from (IX), initially formed. The next attempt consisted in condensation of ethyl α -acetamido- α -methyl- β -phenylpropionate, in toluene medium, with ethyl acetate in presence of anhydrous sodium ethoxide, and yielded a deep red liquid on acidification. This liquid, which develops a positive ferric reaction, has furnished, when heated with 15% hydrochloric acid a resin-like substance which is found to be an acid, devoid of ketonic property. It decolorises bromine water. However, attempts to purify and crystallise the substance have failed.

(IX)

(X)

The above observations suggest that it may be advantageous to prepare the *N*-phthalimido derivative of the amino-acid (IV) and then to effect the condensation of the ethyl ester of the phthalimido derivative with ethyl acetate under the Claisen condition. However, it was not found possible to induce (IV) to condense with phthalic

anhydride under conditions which Vanags and Veinbergs (*Ber*, 1942, 75B, 1558) successfully employed in the case of a number of amines and amino-acids. Whether steric hindrance is at play in the present case due to the adjacent quaternary carbon atom is difficult to say. However, work is in progress along other directions to gain an insight into the manner in which deacetylation and dehydrogenation take place in the formation of isoquinoline derivatives, as mentioned at the outset.

EXPERIMENTAL

α-Carboxy-*α*-acetamido-*β*-phenylpropionic Acid.—Ethyl *α*-carbethoxy-*α*-acetamido-*β*-phenylpropionate (Albertson and Archer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 308) (6.8 g.) was treated with NaOH (2.7 g.) in water (27 c.c.) and refluxed on a steam-bath for about 5 hours. The clear solution was just acidified with HCl (conc.) and the precipitated solid crystallised from aqueous ethanol (charcoal) in colorless rectangular plates (5.2 g.), m.p. 145-46° (decomp.). (Found : N, 5.34. C₁₂H₁₃O₂N requires N, 5.57%).

α-Acetamido-*β*-phenylpropionic Acid.—A mixture of the above dibasic acid (5.2 g.) and water (17 c.c.) was heated under reflux for about 4 hours till CO₂ had ceased to evolve. On cooling, a crystalline solid was obtained, which was filtered and a further quantity was recovered by concentrating the mother-liquor. The solids were crystallised from water in colorless needles (3.4 g.), m.p. 147°. (Found : N, 6.62. C₁₁H₁₃O₂N requires N, 6.76%).

[(*α*-Acetamido-*β*-phenyl)-ethylphenyl Ketone (I : R = Ph).—A mixture of *α*-acetamido-*β*-phenylpropionic acid (10 g.), benzoic anhydride (24 g.) and pyridine (24 g.) was heated on a steam-bath for 6 hours. The mixture after steam-distillation deposited a solid on cooling which was filtered, thoroughly triturated with 5% aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution and then crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles (9 g.), m.p. 107-108°. (Found : N, 5.46. C₁₇H₁₇O₂N requires N, 5.24%).

The 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. 227-28°. (Found : N, 15.58. C₂₃H₂₁O₅N₃ requires N, 15.66%).

2-Methyl-4-benzyl-5-phenyloxazole (II : R = Ph).—A mixture of the above compound (I : R = Ph) (7 g.), nitrobenzene (50 c.c.) and POCl₃ (7 c.c.) was heated under reflux in an oil-bath at 170°-180° for 8 hours. The mixture was cooled, treated with water and then with NaOH solution (15%, 50 c.c.) and finally subjected to steam-distillation till practically free of nitrobenzene. The residue was extracted with ether and removal of the ether left a dark, heavy liquid which distilled at 220-25°/6-7 mm to furnish a brown, mobile liquid which solidified on standing and crystallised from methanol in colorless rectangular plates, m.p. 68-69°. (Found : N, 5.74. C₁₇H₁₅ON requires N, 5.62%). It is insoluble in cold dilute alkali and in HCl (conc.).

Treatment of (I : R = Ph) with H₂SO₄ : Formation of the Sulphonic Acid (III : X = H).—A solution of (I : R = Ph) (6 g.) in H₂SO₄ (conc., 20 c.c.) was allowed to stand at room temperature for 1 hour and then heated on the steam-bath for 1 hour. The cooled solution was poured into water, when a pasty mass was deposited, which turned granular when allowed to stand overnight. The acidic solution did not furnish any product on basification with NaOH.

The solid, readily soluble in aqueous sodium bicarbonate but insoluble in HCl, was crystallised from water (charcoal) in colorless plates (3.8 g.), m.p. 328-30° (decomp.). (Found: N, 4.38; S, 10.15; chem. equiv., 332. $C_{17}H_{15}O_4NS$ requires N, 4.25; S, 9.72%; chem. equiv., 329).

The above sulphonic acid was also obtained by treatment of (II: R = Ph) with concentrated sulphuric acid under identical condition.

(*α*-Acetamido-*β*-*o*-chlorophenyl)-ethylphenyl Ketone (I: R = *o*-Cl.C₆H₄).—The method of preparation was the same as in the case of (I: R = Ph). *α*-Acetamido-*β*-*o*-chlorophenylpropionic acid used was prepared according to the method previously recorded (Ghosh and Dutta, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 755). The ketone was crystallised from aqueous ethanol in colorless rectangular plates, m.p. 105-106°. (Found: N, 4.81. $C_{17}H_{16}(O)_2NCl$ requires N, 4.64%).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. 200°. (Found: N, 14.26. $C_{23}H_{20}O_2N_5Cl$ requires N, 14.53%).

2-Methyl-4 (*o*-chloro)-benzyl-5-phenyloxazole (II: R = *o*-Cl.C₆H₄).—Using (I: R = *o*-Cl.C₆H₄; 12 g.), POCl₃ (12 c.c.) and toluene (80 c.c.) and heating the mixture at 120-30° for 8 hours in an oil-bath, (II: R = *o*-Cl.C₆H₄) was prepared as in the previous case and was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles (7.4 g.), m.p. 87-88°. (Found: N, 4.76. $C_{17}H_{14}ONCl$ requires N, 4.93%). It is insoluble in cold dilute alkali and in HCl (conc.)

Treatment of (I: R = *o*-Cl.C₆H₄) with H₂SO₄: Formation of the Sulphonic Acid (III: X = Cl).—The method of procedure was the same as described previously. The product was obtained as a pasty mass which, when kept in *vacuo*, furnished a granular solid, crystallising as a colorless micro-crystalline powder (m.p. 298-300°; from benzene-ethanol mixture. (Found: N, 3.63; chem. equiv., 360. $C_{17}H_{14}O_4NC!S$ requires N, 3.85%; chem. equiv., 363.5).

(*α*-Acetamido-*β*-*p*-chlorophenyl)-ethylphenyl Ketone (I: R = *p*-Cl.C₆H₄).—The method of preparation was the same as in the case of (I: R = Ph). *α*-Acetamido-*β*-*p*-chlorophenylpropionic acid used was prepared according to the method previously recorded (Ghosh and Dutta, *loc. cit.*). The ketone was crystallised from aqueous ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 151-52°. (Found: N, 4.72. $C_{17}H_{14}O_2NCl$ requires N, 4.64%).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was crystallised from ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. 245-46°. (Found: N, 14.68. $C_{23}H_{20}O_2N_5Cl$ requires N, 14.53%).

Methyl-4 (*p*-chloro)-benzyl-5-phenyloxazole (II: R = *p*-Cl.C₆H₄) was prepared as in the case of (II: R = *o*-Cl.C₆H₄) and was crystallised from aqueous ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 107-108°. (Found: N, 5.21. $C_{17}H_{14}ONCl$ requires N, 4.93%). It is insoluble in cold dilute alkali and in concentrated hydrochloric acid. The same compound (mixed m.p. 107-108°) was obtained when (I: R = *p*-Cl.C₆H₄) was treated with concentrated sulphuric acid, and no trace of any sulphonic acid was formed.

α-Methyl-*α*-amino-*β*-phenylpropionic Acid (IV).—5-Benzylhydantoin (Bucherer and Lieb, *loc. cit.*) (20.4 g.) was treated with NaOH (17.6 g.) in water (75 c.c.) and refluxed on a steam-bath for 24 hours. After treatment with Nuchar, the clear solution was acidified with HCl and filtered to remove a small quantity of impurity. The solution

was evaporated to dryness and the solid residue extracted with anhydrous ethanol. The ethanolic solution was concentrated to 75 c.c. and then treated with pyridine when the amino-acid (14 g.) was precipitated, which was crystallised from aqueous ethanol in colorless rectangular plates, m.p. 263-64°. (Found: N, 7.84. $C_{10}H_{15}O_2N$ requires N, 7.82%). It is moderately soluble in cold water, but readily soluble in hot water and in aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution.

The *acetamido* derivative (VI) was obtained, to the exclusion of any ketone, by treating the above amino-acid with acetic anhydride in presence of pyridine and was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 203-204°. (Found: N, 6.36. $C_{12}H_{15}O_3N$ requires N, 6.33%). The *benzamido* derivative, similarly obtained, was crystallised from ethanol in colorless, micro-crystalline powder, m.p. 204°. (Found: N, 4.82. $C_{17}H_{17}O_3N$ requires N, 4.94%).

Methyl 2-Acetamido-2-methyl-β-phenylpropionate.—A solution of (VI: 29 g.) in anhydrous methanol (180 c.c.) containing H_2SO_4 (conc., 1.8 c.c.) was refluxed on the steam-bath for 6 hours. After distilling off most of the methanol, the residue was poured into water. The solid was triturated with 5% aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution, washed with water and crystallised from water in colorless plates (16 g.), m.p. 119-20°. An analytical sample was dried *in vacuo* over P_2O_5 at 90-95°. (Found: N, 5.72. $C_{13}H_{17}O_3N$ requires N, 5.95%).

1: 3-Dimethyl-3-carbomethoxy-3: 4-dihydroisoquinoline (VIII: R = CO_2Me).—A mixture of the above methyl ester (8 g.), toluene (100 c.c.) and $POCl_3$ (8 c.c.) was heated under reflux in an oil-bath at 115-20° for 7 hours. After distilling off toluene and excess of $POCl_3$, the residue was treated with cold aqueous caustic soda solution (5%) and then washed with water. The dark mass was extracted thrice with HCl (dil.) and the acid extract, on basification with cold dilute caustic soda solution, furnished a reddish gummy mass (2.5 g.). It was somewhat purified by acid-alkali treatment and gave, in benzene solution, a *picrate* which crystallised from benzene in yellow needles, m.p. 182-83°. (Found: C, 50.58; H, 4.32; N, 12.48. $C_{13}H_{15}O_2N.C_6H_5O_2N$, requires C, 51.12; H, 4.03; N, 12.55%).

1: 3-Dimethyl-3-carboxy-3: 4-dihydroisoquinoline (VIII: R = CO_2H).—A mixture of (VIII: R = CO_2Me) (1 g.) and caustic soda (20%, 15 c.c.) was refluxed on the steam-bath for 8 hours. On dilution with water, a clear solution was obtained, which on acidification with HCl (conc.) yielded a solid (0.65 g.). It was crystallised from ethanol (charcoal) in colorless plates, m.p. 241-42°. (Found: N, 6.76. $C_{12}H_{13}O_2N$ requires N, 6.89%). It is soluble in aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution.

2: 4-Dimethyl-4-benzyl-5-dicarbethoxymethylene-4: 5-dihydroxazole (X).—A mixture of the acid (VI: 20 g.), anhydrous benzene (100 c.c.) and thionyl chloride (14.6 g.) was gradually heated in an oil-bath and the temperature was maintained at 55-60° for 1 hour. After removal of the benzene and excess of thionyl chloride *in vacuo*, the resulting acid chloride, when thoroughly cooled, was added gradually to a stirred slurry of ethyl sodiomalonate (16.8 g.) and anhydrous benzene (100 c.c.), set aside overnight and then heated under reflux on a steam-bath for 7 hours. After filtration, benzene was removed *in vacuo*, and the residual liquid was found to distil over a wide range (120°-190°/10-12 mm); it furnished a colorless, heavy liquid (10.5 g.) which solidified on

scratching. The solid was crystallised thrice from petroleum ether (b.p. 60°-80°) in colorless needles, m.p. 97-98°. (Found: C, 66.32; H, 7.21. $C_{18}H_{23}O_3N$ requires C, 66.08; H, 6.67%).

When the above compound (X) was stirred with aqueous NaOH solution (5%) at room temperature, gradually a clear solution was obtained, which on acidification with concentrated hydrochloric acid furnished a solid. After crystallisation from ethanol, it was identified as (VI).

Ethyl α -acetamido- α -methyl- β -phenylpropionate was similarly prepared as the methyl ester and was crystallised from aqueous ethanol in colorless rectangular plates, m.p. 101-102°. (Found: N, 5.34. $C_{14}H_{19}O_3N$ requires N, 5.62%).

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